

Dédalo em Devaneio (2025)

Alúcio Coelho

INSTRUMENTAÇÃO

Violão

Instruções

P+Numeral Romano

Posição. Numeral romano indica a respectiva casa no violão.

Harmônico natural

Multifônico

Arpejo regular de cima para baixo

Golpé no cavalete com a lateral do polegar

G.P.

Pausa longa

A mão direita ataca as cordas à esquerda de onde são apertadas (entre a pestana e a mão esquerda)

Golpé médio de mão direita (no tampo, embaixo da boca)

Golpé agudo de mão esquerda (no tampo, embaixo da 12ª casa)

Golpé grave de mão direita (no tampo, embaixo do cavalete)

Dédalo em Devaneio

Aluíso Coelho

Violão

Ícaro cai ♩ = 40

Escordatura (fade in)

CVII

let vib. 3" bend 2"

CXII

mf *f* *f*

PX

5

dolce *mp* *mf*

bend

rit.

2"

5

natural

mf *f*

a tempo

sultasto let vib.

subito *p*

7

2" 2"

mais rap. possível

(flash blink)

G.P. 1"

mp sul ponticello

11

a tempo

CIX

let vib. 3" bend 2"

CVII

mf *f* *f*

PII

14

dolce *mp* *mf*

rit.

bend

2"

5

PII

mp *ff*

CVII

let vib.

accel.

16 *a tempo* *morrendo* *pp* *mais rápido possível* (flash blink) *mp* *sul ponticello*

19 *Vertigo* $\text{♩} = 70$ *G.P. 1^o* *mp* *sultasto*

23 *rit.* *um pouco mais rápido* *mf* *natural*

25 *CVII*

26 *f* *mf* *rit.*

28 *a tempo* *CVI* *CIX* *mp* *cresc.*

Musical notation for measures 29-30. Measure 29 starts with a forte (*f*) dynamic and a *dim.* (diminuendo) marking. Measure 30 features a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic and a *rit.* (ritardando) marking. A slur labeled CVIII spans across both measures.

Flash back ♩ = 40

Musical notation for measures 31-35. Measure 31 starts with a mezzo-forte (*mf*) dynamic. Measure 32 includes a *f* (forte) dynamic, a *let vib. 3"* marking, and a *bend* instruction. Measure 33 features a *mf* dynamic and a *let vib. 3"* marking. Measure 34 includes a *mf* dynamic and a *let vib. 3"* marking. Measure 35 features a *f* (forte) dynamic. Slurs labeled CVII, CIX, and CXII are present. Fingerings 3, 2, and 6 are indicated.

Musical notation for measures 36-39. Measure 36 includes a *f* (forte) dynamic, a *bend* instruction, and a *2"* marking. Measure 37 features a *mf* dynamic and a *2"* marking. Measure 38 includes a *f* (forte) dynamic, a *let vib. 3"* marking, and a *dolce mp* dynamic. Measure 39 features a *mf* dynamic, a *rit.* marking, and a *bend* instruction. Slurs labeled CV, CVII, and PVIII are present. Fingerings 3, 6, and 5 are indicated.

Musical notation for measures 40-41. Measure 40 starts with a mezzo-piano (*mp*) dynamic. Measure 41 features a *mf* (mezzo-forte) dynamic and an *accel.* (accelerando) marking. A slur labeled CV is present.

Musical notation for measures 42-43. Measure 42 is marked *Rasgueado* and *f* (forte). Measure 43 is marked *sf* (sforzando) and *accel.* (accelerando). Both measures include a *16* marking. A slur labeled CIX is present.

PTSD (♩=108)

45 *mf* *agitato* *subito p*

47 *f* *p* *rit.*

49 *a tempo* *mp* *f*

51 *a tempo* *p*

53 *f*

55 *mf* *jazzy*

57 *sf* 2. (dutch tilt) *mp* *irregular* CIV *a tempo* *mf*

59 *f* CVIII *a tempo* *irregular*

61 CV CVI CVII CVIII CIX CX CXI CXII *quase glissando* *subito p*

62 *f* *rasgueado* *rasgueado* CVIII *mp*

64 *f* CVII *rasgueado* *rasgueado* CIV *mp*

Detailed description of the musical score: The score is written for guitar in a single system with five staves. It begins at measure 57 with a dynamic marking of *sf* and a second ending bracket. A 'dutch tilt' technique is indicated above the first ending. The music continues with a *mp* dynamic and an 'irregular' rhythm. Measure 59 features a *f* dynamic and another 'irregular' rhythm. Measure 61 is marked 'quase glissando' and 'subito p', with measures 61-62 grouped as CV, 63 as CVI, 64 as CVII, 65 as CVIII, 66 as CIX, 67 as CX, 68 as CXI, and 69 as CXII. Measure 62 includes 'rasgueado' techniques. Measure 64 also includes 'rasgueado' techniques. Dynamics range from *sf* to *mp*.

66 a m i m (corte) *f* *mf* *mp* *mf*

69 CVII CIX *mp* *f* *p*

72 *a tempo* *f* *sf*

75 *mf* *jazzy*

77 CIII *mf* *agitato* *subito p*

79 CVI CIX *f*

80

rit. *livre e interrogativo* (fusion) *let vib.*

mp *mf* *pp*

Memória ♩ = 40

84

CVII *let vib.* 3" *bend* 2" *bend* 2"

mf *f* *f* *dolce mp* *mf*

PX PX

88

a tempo *natural* *subito p* *let vib.* 2" *mais rápida possível* (flash blink) G.P. 1"

mf *f* *mp* *sul ponticello*

93

CIX *a tempo* *let vib.* 3" *bend* 2" *bend* 2"

CVII *mf* *f* *f* *dolce mp* *mf*

PII PII

97

CVII *accel.* *a tempo* *repetir ad libitum até desaparecer...* (fade out)

mp *ff* *morrendo* *ppp*